

Past to Future

Towards fully paleo-informed future climate projections

Initial Data Management Plan

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Utrecht University

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1. Data Summary

1.1 Data Re-Use

This project will be re-using many open datasets that provide proxies for historic climate conditions. Project partners are dedicated to citing the datasets they will re-use to give credit to the scientists that have made their data open for re-use. Most of the data that will be re-used will come from the repositories Pangaea.de and NeotomaDB.

During the first General Assembly meeting (November 2025) the consortium will establish guidelines for co-authorship of P2F-related publications and for the citation of (paleo) data sets used in synthesis analyses. These guidelines aim to ensure fair attribution of contributions, particularly for original data sets that are incorporated into broader syntheses.

1.2 New Data

The project will be creating new data in the form of collecting new samples, calculating proxies from those samples, and outputs from Earth System Models (ESM).

The new data collection and proxies calculated from those samples are expected to take up less than 100GB of storage space. The model outputs are expected to be between 10 and 100TB and shared within the project on a platform accessible to all partners. These extremely large datasets will be rigorously reviewed and filtered, and less than 1TB of model outputs will be published. Model data will be possible to re-compute in the future by recording the input parameters given to the models.

The new data will be useful for researchers that study the past climate of Earth, with direct use in other projects such as ClimTip, TipESM and the EMBRACER project.

2. FAIR Data

2.1 Making Data Findable

Datasets will be published on existing popular repositories within the relevant fields of study in the project. The repositories that will be used for publication include Pangaea, Zenodo, Neotoma, all of which are indexed by data search engines and DataCite. The data publications will also be collected on the project data portal as a single location for researchers and the public to find data produced by this project.

The project will also be building a data portal to explore the sources and products of the research (Work Package 7). In this portal all source data will be indexed with a relation to output datasets produced in the course of the project in order to properly cite the work performed by upstream collection projects. During a dedicated Data Portal meeting at the General Assembly Meeting (November 2025) this will further be refined to optimize the use of the Data Portal for the consortium and beyond. Published data will be made available for visualization and corresponding DOI is provided to enable download.

2.2 Making Data Accessible

Datasets generated from this project will be made available with the Creative Commons 4.0 Attribution license. There are no expected datasets from this project that will require restricted-access publication at this time.

2.3 Making Data Interoperable

Datasets from this project will be stored and published primarily in open and highly interoperable data formats.

- Tables will be made available in an open format with a strong preference for the CSV format. Tables or spreadsheets that need more functionalities will be stored in XLSX format and made available in the open Open Document Foundation Spreadsheet format (.ods).
- Simulation models outputs will be stored in NetCDF4 format, an extension of the HDF-5 standard.

2.4 Increase Data Re-Use

Accommodating datasets will be README.txt files and at a minimum DataCite v4 metadata, additional metadata formats may be supplied based on repository and data type. The README.txt files will explain the purpose of the dataset, provide contact information for the creators, list abbreviations and codes, and additional information where appropriate. The README.txt files will be created from a template provided by the research data management community at Utrecht University, and the template can be found [[here](#)].

3. Other Research Outputs

3.1 Code

The code produced by the project will be published to a centralized GitHub Organization for the project. The organization can be found here: [Past to Future EU Horizon](#).

All repositories will come with README.md files to explain the use, installation, citation, and other important information. The README.md files will be created with a template from the research data management community at Utrecht University, and the template can be found [\[here\]](#).

Repositories will be licensed with a permissive and open code license. Repositories will also make use of the GitHub and Zenodo connection that allows Zenodo archives to be created at release versions of software, creating a snapshot repository of the software, and assigning a DOI for the code.

4. Allocation of Resources

Partners on the project will use the storage available at their institution and will use the funds from their respective work packages when funds for storage and computing time are required.

Funds allocated to Work Package 7 will be used to host the portal web infrastructure, and the storage needs to support the data in the portal where needed.

Funds for storage facilities were not secured to share large scale data across different partner organizations of the consortium. Therefore, the consortium will pursue funding for large scale storage accessible to all parties together with ClimTip.

5. Data Security

5.1 Unauthorized Access

The data in the course of the project research will be stored either on individual institutional storage systems or the TeamSite/SharePoint environment of Utrecht University.

All systems will have at minimum a named user access system, with file level permissions, most institutions also require multi-factor authentication.

5.2 Data Integrity

Datasets that are needed in the long term must be stored on a reliable storage system with robust backups. Long term institutional storage must follow 3-2-1 backup rules to avoid data loss. Individual research computers must not be the sole storage location for important data sets; they must be backed up to a reliable system. Partners are

encouraged to store data in multiple locations. Datasets that are included here are observations, calculated proxies, and analysis.

Datasets that can be recovered, either by re-downloading the data from a repository or re-calculated from the modelling software, can be stored on less reliable storage. This includes storage systems that are scratch disks or temporary storage for high performance computing (HPC) systems or the storage of a partner's computer.

6. Ethics

There are no ethical or legal issues that we can foresee. There is no personal data generated within the project.

7. Other Issues

Nothing to report.